

REPRESENT: Research on Practices around Religion, Ethnicity and Society

Call for Papers

REPRESENT: Research on Practices around Religion, Ethnicity and Society is a new **biannual** (spring and autumn), peer-reviewed, cross-disciplinary and interdisciplinary English-language journal that covers a broad range of themes across the humanities and social sciences.

Key focus areas of *REPRESENT*

- Critical analysis of public policies and popular practices related to ethnicity, race, religion, and society, with a focus on adherence to constitutional morality and reform-oriented recommendations.
- Qualitative and quantitative, data-driven analyses of participation by gender, racial, and ethnic groups in social, economic, and political domains.
- Representations of gender, religion, ethnicity, and society in social, political, and educational institutions.
- Tracking and offering critical analysis of media representations of gender, race, and ethnicity in India and the world.
- Fostering counter-narratives, decolonial perspectives and community media practices.

Important Date

31 March
Paper
submission
deadline for
Spring Issue

30 September
Paper
submission
deadline for
Autumn Issue

Submission Process

- Visit the Website and submit articles using the online system.
- No Article Processing Fees.
- Double blind peer review.
- Open access article publication, with digital archiving and DOI.

<https://represent.co.in/>

admin@represent.co.in

[REPRESENTJournal](https://www.facebook.com/REPRESENTJournal)

[@Represent_IN](https://twitter.com/Represent_IN)

Call for Paper for an interdisciplinary journal

REPRESENT: Research on Practices around Religion Ethnicity, and Society

This is a general call for a new biannual, peer-reviewed, interdisciplinary journal.

Synopsis

REPRESENT: Research on Practices around Religion, Ethnicity and Society is a new biannual (spring and autumn), peer-reviewed, cross-disciplinary and interdisciplinary English-language journal that covers a broad range of themes across the humanities and social sciences.

The title *REPRESENT* indicates the focus of the journal as a critical academic space for publishing *Research on Practices around Religion, Ethnicity, and Society*, encompassing divergent issues of ethnic and cultural-religious minorities, and gender, including their representations in media, films, and popular culture, as well as in social, political, and educational institutions.

REPRESENT seeks to promote critical study of the complex interplay among media and fields such as social, political, cultural, spatial, intellectual and more. It will hence develop as a new academic space in public discourse by making critical interventions, offering fresh insights, countering and reframing established narratives, and setting a new agenda vis-à-vis race and ethnicity.

Based out of Kolkata, India, while *REPRESENT* will focus on South Asia, but being an online journal, we are open to articles from all underrepresented areas in the Global South as well as understudied themes around gender, race, and ethnicity in the world at large.

The Journal is double-blind peer-reviewed and open-access, although we do not currently charge any article processing fees. However, we will not publish any article without rigorous peer review and will not respond to or entertain any inquiries regarding expedited processing and publication.

REPRESENT is published by SABAR Institute, Kolkata, registered as a trust under the Trust Act of West Bengal, that focuses on addressing social disparities, fostering social cohesion, and promoting social justice through evidence-based research aimed at creating an inclusive India and the world. Besides, SABAR Institute also runs an inter-faith initiative, [Know Your Neighbour](#), in Kolkata and beyond. Visit the website of the [SABAR Institute](#) to know more about our work.

Key Focus Areas of *REPRESENT*

- Critical analysis of public policies and popular practices related to ethnicity, race, religion, and society, with a focus on adherence to constitutional morality and reform-oriented recommendations.
- Qualitative and quantitative, data-driven analyses of participation by gender, racial, and ethnic groups in social, economic, and political domains.

- Representations of gender, religion, ethnicity, and society in social, political, and educational institutions.
- Tracking and offering critical analysis of media representations of gender, race, and ethnicity in India and the world.
- Fostering counter-narratives, decolonial perspectives, and community media practices.

Types of Articles

Research Article: A standard research article should be between 5000 and 8000 words, including references.

Perspective/Commentary Pieces: Sharp, concise, and well-argued 2000-2500-word pieces including references.

Review Essay: Reviews of films, OTT series, or a set of books on similar themes, 2000-3000 words including references.

Book/Film Review: 1000-1500 words

Interview (In special cases, interviews of renowned authors, subject experts, and researchers may be considered, subject to necessary review): 1500-2000 words

Reference Style: In-text citations, and [APA 7th edition Referencing style](#).

While online submission of articles will remain open throughout the year, manuscripts received by 31st March will be considered for the Spring Issue, and those received by 30th September will be considered for the Autumn Issue.

Editorial Board

Editors

Dr Kaifia Ancer Laskar, Assistant Professor, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, [Aliah University](#), Kolkata, India. [ORCID](#) [Google Scholar](#)

Dr Mohammad Reyaz, Assistant Professor, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, [Aliah University](#), Kolkata, India. [ORCID](#) [Google Scholar](#)

Consulting Editor

Dr Md Zakaria Siddiqui, Associate Professor, Department of Economics, [Jamia Millia Islamia](#), New Delhi, India. [ORCID](#) [Google Scholar](#)

Editorial Advisory Member(s)

Sabir Ahamed, National Research Coordinator, [Pratichi Institute](#), Kolkata, India, and Lead, SABAR Institute, Kolkata, India. [Google Scholar](#)

Visit the website for more details: <https://represent.co.in/>.

Follow Social Media for regular updates:

Fb: REPRESENTJournal

X: @Represent_IN